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Artist Videos

2021-2022

Deliverable 4.5.1

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A-Place

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Artist Videos (2021-2022)

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Executive Summary

This is a report on the video art productions created during the third year of the project which have been commissioned by the LOOP Barcelona festival and screened in its 2022 edition. Two video works were commissioned:

- by Domènec, as artist-in-residence, to carry out a research work focused on the urban context of Sant Just Desvern, Barcelona. With the video Walden 7 or Life In The Cities, the artist investigated an emblematic social housing building designed by Ricardo Bofill.

- by Sindihogar/Sindillar, winners of the 2022 open call on video art. Their project El lugar que habito (The place I inhabit) aims to explore the controversies experienced by migrant women within the context of Barcelona.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and target group

For the past twenty years, Screen Projects has organized LOOP Barcelona, an international meeting point to showcase the latest artistic productions related to video art, the moving image and the ever-expanding field of audiovisual artworks. From its very start, one of its foremost concerns has been how to offer artists the opportunity to reflect and enrol in practices that strengthen their social implication. Therefore, most of the artistic practices that LOOP supports tend to capture the complex layers that animate public space and the various constructs that define people's sense of belonging, as well as intimating the ways in which they relate to the world. In short, we assume that artists are always eager to uncover the symbolic construction of place, a hidden layer that seldom manifests itself in material terms, and this is precisely what LOOP intends to help bring out in a bid to widen the reach of creative placemaking.

This report contains a description of the process leading to the commission of the two video art productions presented in the A-Place section of the 2022 edition of the LOOP festival: Walden 7 or Life In The Cities by Domènec and El lugar que habito (The place I inhabit) by Sindihogar/Sindillar.

1.2. Contribution of partners

Screen Projects, the organization that manages the LOOP Barcelona festival, has been the partner in charge of organizing the open call and selecting the artists-in-residence. Representatives from La Salle and Screen Projects were part of the jury of the open call. Other A-Place partners have contributed to the dissemination of the call and of the awarded work.

1.3. Relations to other activities in the project

During 2022, the video La città dentro by ZimmerFrei collective, produced by LOOP in 2019-2020, was presented in *Pame Kaimakli Festival 2022* organized by Urban Gorillas (Nicosia) and *Urban Visions. Beyond the Ideal City 2022* organized by City Space Architecture (Bologna), both A-Place partners. Continuing with this collaboration, LOOP intends to screen in 2023 Domènec and Sindihogar videos' in these two festivals.

Also, Luisa Bravo (City Space Architecture) and Leandro Madrazo (La Salle) participated in a LOOP Professional Meeting organized in the A-Place section of the LOOP Barcelona Festival.

2. Artist-in-residence production

2.1. Intent and goals

The artists-in-residence grant aims to produce a video artwork that explores the notion of place. The topic chosen by the invited artist, Domènec (Barcelona, 1962), was the life in the Walden 7 building, and emblematic building designed by Ricardo Bofill Taller de Arquitectura in the late 1970s located in Sant Just Desvern, a town in the metropolitan area of Barcelona. Through research on the building's physical, historical and social evolution, the artist produced a video that offers a unique perspective on the construction of this place, of "being in place" and the sense of belonging.

Domènec is an artist known for his conceptual reflections, and has a history of creating sculpture and videographic work, along with installations and public space interventions that all centre around the architectural project as an important and intricate concept in the modern tradition.

2.2. Commissioned project

Domènec

Walden 7 or The Life in the Cities (2021, 35 min)

<https://www.a-place.eu/en/media-production/50>

To carry out [Walden 7 or Life In The Cities](#), the artist used archival images and interviews to trace the evolution of the building from its original design to its current state, and structured a series of testimonies around a conversation with the architect's sister and co-author of the project, Anna Bofill, who is also an architect and has lived in the building for over thirty years. Her perspectives and experiences offer a unique insight into the relationship between the building and its inhabitants.

Figure 1. *Walden 7 or Life In The Cities*, by Domènec. View of the exhibition at COAC, Barcelona.
Source: LOOP Festival

On November 7, 2022, LOOP Barcelona organized a premiere of the video at the Col·legi d'Arquitectes de Catalunya (COAC) in Barcelona, with the participation of the artist. On the same occasion, LOOP presented the festival programme to the press, which helped to give greater visibility to the video work. The exhibition was on view until 17 November 2022 (Figure 1).

3. Open call production

3.1. Intent and goals

In order to support the creative endeavours of artists, LOOP Barcelona launched a call for proposals to attract and engage a wide range of participants to generate ideas about the concept of place in all its possible expressions and dimensions. The call aimed to support projects that critically examine established ideas and traditional approaches to the symbolic creation of space and sense of belonging. These types of artworks are intended to promote public discussion and shape social constructions. The ultimate goal is to promote the idea of active citizenship and shared public spaces, which are central to the A-Place project.

3.2. Open call process

The call was announced on January 2022 and it was advertised in the [A-Place website](#) (Figure 2) and in the [LOOP website](#) (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Announcement of the call in A-Place website

Figure 3. Announcement of the call in LOOP website

The documentation of the call (Figure 4) included:

- A short description of the project A-Place
- A presentation of LOOP Barcelona, the issuer of the call
- The object and purpose of the call
- The terms and conditions - Participants Eligibility
 - Project Characteristics
 - Awarded Grant
 - Selection Criteria
 - How to Submit
 - Application Deadline and Calendar
 - Acceptance of Terms

Figure 4. Documentation of the open call

3.3. The jury

An international jury was assembled to ease the complex task of choosing a winner for the A-Place Open Call 2022. The jury was composed of the following members:

- **Leandro Madrazo.** Project Coordinator of A-Place, full professor and director of the research group ARC Engineering and Architecture at La Salle. His teaching interests focus on the integration of architecture theory and representation, art and media, as well as on housing studies and design methodology. He has been the coordinator of various research projects, such as HOUSING@21.EU (2003-06), OIKODOMOS (2007-09, 2010-11), and OIKONET (2013-16), all funded by EACEA. He has been co-coordinator of PROHABIT (2015-18) and has led the UMVA programme, carried out in collaboration with LOOP Festival, from 2012 to 2017.

- **Ramón Parramón.** Artist, researcher and professor. Director and founder of IDENSITAT @identsitat a collective project, through which he develops his research practice as an artist and cultural manager. He is the deputy director of EINA Centre Universitari de Disseny i Art de Barcelona, UAB. Previously, he has been director of the ACVIC. Centre d'Arts Contemporànies (2010-2018) and has been part of the curatorial team of Co-habitar at Fabra i Coats Centre d'Art Contemporani de Barcelona (2016-2017). He specializes in the intersection of artistic practices and social spaces and has extensively published on the topic, including articles in various books and magazines.

- **pli-ē collective.** A research and curatorial group formed by Eva Paià, Marina Ribot Pallicer and Angelica Tognetti. Since February 2021 they managed the Sala d'Art Jove, a space promoted by the Catalan Youth Agency of the Generalitat de Catalunya.

- **Victoria Sacco** (A-Place partner). LOOP A-Place Coordinator & LOOP City Screen Coordinator, curator and professor. She is the editor of *Muntadas. Con/Textos III: An Anthology of Critical Texts*, published by La Virreina Centre de la Imatge (2020), and writes for the journal *La Maleta de Portbou*. Since 2010, she has been teaching at the ESDi School of Design in Barcelona and since 2014 she has been collaborating in LOOP Barcelona festival. Previously, she worked as project coordinator and later as co-director of the arts and science foundation Quo Artis. She is currently working with Pedro G. Romero and Antoni Muntadas.

The criteria to select the works were the following:

- The artistic merit of the proposal.
- The consolidated professional career of the artist/s.
- The innovative way of exploring the concept of creative placemaking.
- The implication of local social agents, associations or collectives.
- The understanding of all the aspects and viability implicit in a video production of this kind.

The jury was convened weeks in advance. In order to facilitate the jury's task, LOOP made a pre-selection of projects. Carolina Ciuti, artistic director of the festival and Victoria Sacco, coordinator of the A-Place project at LOOP, were responsible for short-listing the projects. However, the jury received the complete list of all the productions submitted, in case they wanted to review any of them. The jury met online on 3 March 2022 to make the final selection..

3.4. Awarded production

We received 73 project proposals, with applications coming from 13 European countries. The projects submitted revealed a wide variety of approaches to building and engaging communities in art-based placemaking processes. After a long debate, the jury decided to assign the award to "El lugar que habito" (The place I inhabit) by Sindihogar/Sindillar. The winner was announced on the [Instagram channel](#) (Figure 5) and in the [News section](#) of A-Place (Figure 6). The news were also disseminated by other channels outside A-Place (Figure 7).

Figure 5. Announcement of the winner in the A-Place Instagram channel

The screenshot shows the A-Place website's news section. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the A-Place logo and menu items: Activities, Media Productions, Netplaces, Open Calls, Dissemination, News, and About. Below the navigation, there is a link to '< Go Back' and the date '15 March 2022'. The main heading is 'Announcing the winners - Video Production Open Call'. To the left of the text is a graphic with the A-Place logo, a play button icon, and the text 'Video Production Open Call Winner announced 2022'. The text on the right reads: 'We are happy to announce the results of the third "A-PLACE - Video Production Open Call", in its 2022 edition. We received 73 project proposals, with applications coming from 13 European countries. The projects submitted have revealed a wide variety of approaches to building and engaging communities in art-based placemaking processes. The quantity and quality of the proposals have led the jury to an exciting and complex deliberation process. We would like to thank everyone who submitted a proposal for their interest and efforts. Finally, the jury decided to assign the award to the project entitled: "The Place I Inhabit" by SINDIHOGAR collective. SINDIHOGAR is the first independent trade union of cleaning and caring workers in Spain. Funded in 2012, it actively struggles for the dignity of caring work and the Migrant Women's rights. Because of their strong commitment to affirm the role of migrant women as cultural producers, they have been engaged in several artistic projects. "The Place I Inhabit" focuses on the dichotomy between public and private spaces of the city of Barcelona and the paradox of caring. As they state: "Our voices and experience of the city are in direct contrast with the image constructed by the 'Barcelona Brand' (...). For this very reason, this project aims to give a turn to the 'outsider' narrative, bringing back our voices and bodies to the centre." The video will be exhibited in the 2022 edition of the LOOP Festival which will take place in Barcelona, in November. The jury members were Leandro Madrazo (School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona and A-Place Project Coordinator), Ramón Parramón (IDENSITAT, Barcelona) and Pti-é collective (Sala d'Art Jove, Barcelona). Open Call Coordinator: Victoria Sacco'. At the bottom, there is a dark footer with the A-Place logo and navigation links: Main sections (Project), Legal Information (Privacy policy), and Social networks (Instagram).

Figure 6. Announcement of the winner in the A-Place News section

The screenshot shows the 'exibart' website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'RadArts', 'Insertar residencia', 'Agenda', 'Insertar exposición o evento', 'Regístrate', and 'Iniciar sesión'. Below this, there is a banner for 'ART MADRID 18 ANIVERSARIO PALACIO DE CIBELIS - MADRID'. The main headline reads: 'Sindihogar/Sindillar gana la tercera edición de 'A-Place Video Production Open Call''. To the right of the headline, there is a large number '15' indicating the date '15 MARZO 2022'. Below the headline, there are three buttons: 'Suscribirse a la newsletter', 'Insertar residencias', and 'Insertar exposición o evento'. On the left side, there is a section titled 'CONVOCATORIAS de Redacción' with social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and LinkedIn. Below this is a video player showing a thumbnail for 'A-Place Video Production Open Call 2022' with a 'Winner announced' banner. The video player also features logos for 'A-Place', 'LOOP BCN', and 'Co-funded by the Creative Europe Programme of the European Union'. To the right of the video player, there is an 'Agenda' section with a search bar and filters for 'Exposiciones y eventos', 'Eventos de hoy', 'En curso y futuros', 'Pasados, en curso y futuros', and 'Buscar eventos web'. Below the agenda, there are buttons for 'Ver más lecturas' and 'Últimos artículos'.

Figure 7. Announcement of the winner in the A-Place News section

Sindihogar/ Sindillar

El lugar que habito (The place I Inhabit) (2022, 23 min)

<https://www.a-place.eu/en/media-production/51>

[El lugar que habito](#) (Figure 8) is a visual essay delves into the experiences of migrant women working as domestic workers in Barcelona. It critically examines the invisibility and lack of agency these women face in shaping cultural heritage and their segregation into domestic labour in private households. The work also highlights the significance of recognising the sense of belonging and active participation of migrant women in public spaces. These issues are explored through various perspectives and observations, accompanied by a soundscape of a diverse voices to emphatically guide the viewer through a multidimensional journey through private and public spaces.

Figure 8. *The Place I Inhabit*, by Sindihogar. Exhibition view. Casa Elizalde, Barcelona.
Source: LOOP Barcelona festival

The video was premiered at [La Casa Elizalde](#), Barcelona, from 8 November to 23 December, 2022. Together with the video, there was an exhibition of the work done by Sindihogar (Figure 9).

Figure 9. *The Place I Inhabit*, by Sindihogar. Exhibition view. Casa Elizalde, Barcelona.
Source: LOOP Barcelona festival

In the following days, there was a round table and a guided tour of the exhibition.

- Wednesday 23 November 2022, at 19:00

Round table: the role of women migrants in the public space, with the participation of Áurea Patricia Ayón, from Sindihogar/Sindillar, Isabel Segura, historian, and Victoria Sacco, LOOP commissioner.

Participants were asked to consider the following questions: How do women live, develop, experience and shape the public spaces? How does the law on foreigners affect the lives of migrant women in these spaces? What role do state institutions play in these issues? Through the discussion, the goal is to reflect on the experiences and contributions of migrant women in public spaces.

- Wednesday 14 December 2022 19:00 - 20:00

Guided tour at the exhibition The Place I Inhabit